

ORIGIN, TREATMENT, PREVENTION OF ITSENKO-CUSHING SYNDROME IN MODERN INTERPRETATION.

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Abstract. Cushing's syndrome is a pathological condition of the body characterized by an excessive amount of the hormone cortisol produced by the adrenal glands. The main cause of the disease is the disruption of regulatory mechanisms responsible for the functioning of the hypothalamus-pituitary-adrenal system.

The disease can appear at any age; can be congenital or acquired. The main symptoms of the disease: disorder of fat metabolism, destruction of bone tissue, damage to the heart and blood vessels, high blood glucose levels, mental disorders.

Key words: Cushing's syndrome, types of Itsenko-Cushing's syndrome, other symptoms of endocrine disease.

ПРОИСХОЖДЕНИЕ, ЛЕЧЕНИЕ, ПРОФИЛАКТИКА СИНДРОМА ИЦЕНКО-КУШИНГА В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ ИНТЕРПРЕТАЦИИ

Аннотация. Синдром Кушинга – патологическое состояние организма, характеризующееся избыточным количеством гормона кортизола, вырабатываемого надпочечниками. Основной причиной заболевания является нарушение регуляторных механизмов, отвечающих за функционирование гипоталамо-гипофизарно-надпочечниковой системы.

Заболевание может появиться в любом возрасте; может быть врожденным или приобретенным. Основные симптомы заболевания: нарушение жирового обмена, разрушение костной ткани, поражение сердца и сосудов, повышенный уровень глюкозы в крови, психические расстройства.

Ключевые слова: синдром Кушинга, разновидности синдрома Иценко-Кушинга, другие симптомы эндокринных заболеваний.

If not treated, Cushing's syndrome causes serious life-threatening complications: heart or lung failure, renal hypertension, frequent bone fractures, myopathy, etc. Therefore, at the first signs of pathology, an experienced endocrinologist should be contacted.

Itsenko-Cushing syndrome is a pathological condition caused by excessive production of the hormone cortisol by the cortex of the adrenal glands or long-term use of glucocorticoid drugs. In women, the pathology is 10 times more frequent than in men, and in most cases it develops at the age of 25-40. Taking into account the effect on absolutely all body systems, without treatment, the symptoms of Cushing's syndrome are constantly increasing, which leads to irreversible consequences and life-threatening complications.

Types of Itsenko-Cushing syndrome

Symptoms of Itsenko-Cushing syndrome directly depend on the form of the pathology. It can be classified as follows.

endogenous: related to excessive production of cortisol by the body;

exogenous: caused by taking glucocorticoid drugs.

Depending on the level of ACTH:

Dependent on ACTH: develops due to excessive production of the substance;

ACTH-independent: Caused by spontaneous oversecretion of cortisol.

When diagnosing Itsenko-Cushing syndrome, it is very important to accurately determine the form, because the treatment tactics depend on it.

Symptoms of Cushing's syndrome

The main symptom of Cushing's syndrome is severe obesity. At the same time, excess body weight is unevenly distributed - fat accumulates in the face, neck, chest, back and abdomen. Limbs tend to become thinner. The face is moon-shaped, with feverish purple-red redness and acne.

1. Other symptoms of endocrine disease:
2. muscle atrophy, muscle weakness;
3. fragility of the bone skeleton, tendency to fracture;
4. bad posture (kyphosis, scoliosis);
5. pale skin, clearly visible vascular pattern;
6. bright stretch marks (stretch marks) on the abdomen, chest and buttocks;
7. high blood pressure;
8. arrhythmia;
9. decreased vision;
10. frequent headaches;
11. menstrual disorders;
12. sexual dysfunction,
13. quick fatigue;
14. prone to neuroses.

Causes of Cushing's syndrome

Adrenal glands are enlarged in Cushing's syndrome. As a result, the glands begin to secrete a large amount of corticosteroid hormones, which provokes the typical symptoms of the disease.

The main causes of the development of Cushing's syndrome:

- genetic predisposition;
 - the presence of a pituitary adenoma;
 - tumor formation of the adrenal cortex;
 - oncological processes of other organs - lungs, pancreas;
 - past infections affecting the central nervous system (meningitis, influenza);
 - traumatic brain injury;
 - intoxication of the body;
 - hormonal imbalance (for example, during pregnancy or menopause);
 - long-term use of drugs containing glucocorticoids.
- Treatment methods for Cushing's syndrome

Therapeutic treatment

The main goal of therapeutic treatment is to eliminate the mechanism of excess production of adrenal hormones, normalize the level of cortisol in the body, and eliminate the unpleasant symptoms of the disease. For this, first of all, the doctor gives the patient the necessary recommendations for lifestyle changes - following a low-calorie diet and increasing physical activity.

Drug therapy includes the use of the following drugs:

- drugs that suppress the production of hormones by the adrenal cortex;
- drugs that lower blood sugar;
- diuretics;
- cardiac glycosides;
- antidepressants or tranquilizers;
- Treatment for Cushing's syndrome includes radiation therapy and chemotherapy. These methods allow to achieve good therapeutic results in the fight against pathology.

Surgery

In most cases, Cushing's syndrome develops due to tumor growth, which must be surgically removed. Surgical treatment is performed using modern minimally invasive methods. The use of high-tech equipment allows our specialists to eliminate the pathology almost bloodlessly, without affecting nearby tissues.

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